

FEATURES OF CULTIVATION AND SEED PRODUCTION OF THE ASPARAGUS BEAN VARIETY "OLTIN SOCH"

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Annotation. The article provides information on the study of economically valuable traits of the early-ripening variety "Oltin Soch" of asparagus beans (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp. *subsp. sesquipedalis* (L.) Verdc.) when grown in Uzbekistan. The yield in technical ripeness (green beans) is 5.7-6.2 t/ha, and the yield of ripe seeds is 0.17-0.19 t/ha.

Keywords: asparagus beans, plants, vegetation period, yield, seeds.

Introduction. The versatile useful properties of leguminous crops (use in crop rotation to increase soil fertility, nutritional properties, use in cooking, etc.) indicate the need to introduce their varieties, create new varieties and develop technology for their cultivation and seed production to expand the sowing area in the country.

Asparagus or nvegetable beans (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp. *subsp. sesquipedalis* (L.) Verdc.) is a widespread crop in many countries of the world. In various countries, scientists conduct research on the study of variety samples, the identification of promising sources of economically valuable traits, the selection of new varieties and the reproduction of asparagus bean seeds [4, 5].

Vegetable beans are rich in iron, calcium, phosphorus and other trace elements, as well as vitamins C, A, E, and Zn. It is a good source of easily digestible dietary protein, close to meat and fish protein in its essential amino acids. In green pods, its content reaches 4%, and in dry seeds - up to 32%. Due to their dietary properties, beans are recommended for heart, liver and kidney diseases, gastritis, reduced secretion of the stomach, and tuberculosis.

In studies by Nwosu J.N. et al [7] the crude fiber (CFC), dietary fiber (DFC), total protein, and total fat contents varied from 4.10 to 6.51%, 16.71 to 23.49%, 22.45 to 28.11%, and 0.59 to 2.00%, respectively.

According to Chalise B. et al [3] in the study of asparagus beans in the soil and climatic conditions of Nepal in the autumn-winter period, the number of

days from germination to the beginning of flowering and harvesting varied from 35 to 42 days for early-ripening varieties and from 52 to 61 days for late-ripening varieties. In terms of yield at technical ripeness (green pods), the variety "HRDA SB-001" surpassed other varieties with a maximum yield of 28.99 t/ha

In the study of Pandey Y.R. et al [8] of varieties of asparagus beans, the largest (0.9 cm in diameter) and longest pods (25.6 cm), as well as the highest yield of green pods (4.97 t/ha) were in the variety "IT 86F-2062-5". The early-ripening variety 'Prakash' had the smallest in diameter (0.67 cm) and shortest (16.2 cm) pods, as well as the lowest yield - 2.44 t/ha.

Asparagus beans, with enough moisture, give a large harvest of beans. However, it also tolerates short-term stressful conditions, such as drought and heat. Therefore, in some countries, physiological research is carried out in these areas [4, 6].

In Uzbekistan, asparagus beans are an unconventional crop. In previous years, samples of asparagus beans were introduced from the World Vegetable Center (WorldVeg). As a result of study and selection, a new bush variety of asparagus beans "Oltin Soch" was created.

Methods. The studies were carried out following the Methodological Guidelines for Environmental Testing of Vegetable Crops. Cultivation and seed production were carried out following existing methods [1,2]. Seeds were sown to a depth of 3-4 cm. The seed sowing rate was 30-35 kg/ha.

The optimal ratio of phosphorus to potassium, necessary for the normal development of beans, is 1.5:1.0. During the growing season, a total 10-12 irrigations are needed.

Results. A feature of the asparagus bean variety "Oltin Soch" is its bush shape. This allows you to place plants in one row on a bed 70 cm wide with a distance between plants of 15-20 cm when growing on green pods.

The variety "Oltin soch" is early-ripening. The optimal temperature for the growth and development of plants is +18...+25 C⁰. The variety "Oltin soch" is suitable for growing during spring sowing in mid-April, as well as during summer sowing in July-August as a second crop after harvesting cereals, vegetables and other crops.

Beans belong to self-pollinating crops and pollination occurs in the bud in the morning before the flower opens. In Uzbekistan, when the temperature in summer rises to +35 ... +42C⁰ and the relative humidity drops to 40%, the

flowers begin to fall, and the number of deformed beans increases. Therefore, during this period, it is necessary to irrigate every week.

The rosette of the leaves of the plant is medium-leafy. 30-35 days after the emergence of seedlings, the plants begin to bloom. During flowering, many purple flowers are formed. New flowers are constantly formed for 1.5 - 2.0 months and therefore, the formation of beans is continuous. 8-10 days after the beginning of flowering, the first beans are ready for harvesting. As a result, if the beans are not harvested in time, then one plant will be like ripe beans and new green pods. It should be noted that regular harvesting of green beans from the plant contributes to the appearance of more new flowers, which, in the future, provides an increase in the overall yield.

The plant forms serpentine pods (beans) 36 cm long and 0.7 cm in diameter. The first harvesting of green beans in technical ripeness was carried out on the 47 - 50th day after the appearance of mass shoots and green beans were harvested every 3-5 days as they appeared. During the growing season, 4-6 harvests were carried out. When grown in the foothills of the Tashkent region, the average height of the plants was 42 cm and the diameter of the leaf rosette was 52 cm. The yield of green pods in technical ripeness was 5.7 t/ha with 99% of the marketability of the products.

When grown in the conditions of the Fergana Valley, where the climate is warmer, the plants develop better. The average height of the plants was 53 cm and the diameter of the leaf rosette was 59 cm. The yield of green pods at technical ripeness was 6.2 t/ha with a high (99%) marketability of beans.

When growing beans for seed purposes, it is important to conduct timely approbations and time to collect seeds from plants. When seeding the asparagus bean variety "Oltin Soch", it is necessary to take into account that due to the constant formation of new flowers, the pods on the plant ripen alternately. To harvest ripe beans, it is better to use two-three times manual harvesting. Do not take the very first formed beans, as well as the last harvest, for seeds. Otherwise, on the first ripe beans in hot weather, the surface dries out and cracks, which leads to a deterioration in quality. The last beans formed are usually smaller in size and have small seeds.

The biological ripeness of the seeds of the "Oltin Soch" variety came on the 75-80th day. On one plant, 25-35 beans are formed, which first have a light green color, and then turn yellow. It should be noted that the beans themselves do not fully open when ripe and the seeds do not crumble in the field.

The yield of seeds from ripe beans in the foothills of the Tashkent region was 1.7 c/ha, and in the Fergana Valley, it reached 1.9 c/ha. Each bean contains 20-23 seeds. The weight of 1000 seeds of asparagus beans is 190 g. The length of the seed is 1,0 cm and diameter - 0.5 cm. Seeds are elongated-kidney-shaped. The color of the seed at biological ripeness is red-brown, the color of the scar is dark, and the surface of the seed is smooth, with a matte tint.

Conclusions. Studies have shown that the variety of asparagus beans "Oltin soch" is well adapted to the soil and climatic conditions of Uzbekistan. Taking into account the biological features of this heat-loving crop in the conditions of the Fergana Valley, the yield of green pods, as well as seeds of this variety, was higher than when grown in the foothills of the Tashkent region. It is necessary to follow varietal agricultural techniques and carry out timely approbations and selections to obtain high-quality seeds.

In Uzbekistan, green beans with seeds or ripe asparagus bean seeds are cooked. They are a high-calorie product for the preparation of salads, porridge, soups and other dishes. The green mass of plants is a nutritious fodder for animals. The variety "Oltin soch" is successfully combined in crop rotation with vegetables and other crops and improves soil fertility.

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